

Scientific article

A novel metric to compare wind farm layouts and identify trends in the layout optimization problem

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Abstract: *During the design phase of a wind farm, turbine positions are optimized based on selected performance metrics, such as annual energy production (AEP) or net present value (NPV). Different layouts are typically compared through such performance metrics. However, this approach does not allow to differentiate layouts that have the same performance. Furthermore, comparing layouts visually is only effective when the number of wind turbines is small. In this work, we propose a model-agnostic metric named layout field error based on the superposition of bi-dimensional Gaussian distributions. It enables both qualitative and quantitative comparison between different layouts. It produces maps highlighting the regions of the domain predominantly occupied by the turbines and quantifies the differences between layouts using a single numerical value based solely on turbine locations. This metric is to compare layouts optimized to maximize either AEP or NPV. Results show that AEP tends to concentrate turbines in high-wind-speed regions, whereas NPV results in a tradeoff that also favors regions with shallower water depths.*

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